

On origins of life and the cosmozoic theory - Discussion on evidence that ultra space chemicals gave rise to life

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Abstract

The origin of life is a fascinating topic to consider. After the period of raining meteorites, there appeared to be a small life form, and this was as early as 3.5 billion years ago. The first traces of life on Earth are often assumed to be single-celled organisms that feast on the produce of hydrothermal vents. The evidence of early life on Earth was preserved in fossils, allowing human civilization to combine these ancient life forms with the mechanisms of evolution, beginning endless theorizing and vivid imagination. However, the main point of debate resides on the origin, raising questions about the first components of life and how Earth was able to form life. The answer could come to explain for humans at least the first two questions of "Where Do We Come From? What Are We? Where Are We Going?" Noticing the overwhelming support of chemical evolution, this article was written in defense of the theory of naturalistic panspermia by first affirming the possibility of panspermia then disassembling the popular theory of chemical evolution.

1. Possibility of Alien Life

Even before proving anything, one must identify if there is even any possibility that other planets that form life before Earth exist. NASA estimates the universe to be around 13.7 billion years old, while the Earth is only 4.5 billion years old (Whitlock et al., 2023). The first life on Earth appeared about one billion years after the creation of Earth, and it is worth noting that Earth was formed terrestrially within 10-20 million years (Qingzhu et al., 2002). Hence, there is now a vacancy of roughly 9 billion years between the formation of the universe and the earliest formation of Earth, which would only take 10-20 million years. This means that other planets can form like Earth did for early life during this gap. This is where organic molecules can be formed and delivered to Earth. If Earth could raise life after five hundred million years by the reasoning of chemical evolution, the universe had plenty of opportunities within

the 9.2 billion years' vacancy for life to form outside of the mass of rock and water that was Earth, making it more probable that there were basic organisms that arrived at Earth.

2. The First Lifeform

For the first thought process, now that the possibility of panspermia is supported, assume that the primordial soup was in some degree of isolation and that the first life present was a fully formed microorganism existing in spatial ices and meteorites. To validate the theory, the building blocks to life must be able to form in space, survive in space as well as crash, and thrive on Earth. Life is understood to revolve around DNA. Life on Earth is a DNA species, and the existence of DNA relies on twenty different amino acids. At the same time, in the very low density of clouds of molecules and dust particles in the interstellar medium of space, single atoms of carbon can react with carbon monoxide and ammonia molecules to form amino acid-like molecules and assemble into peptides once dense enough. Many have been detected in meteorites along with carbohydrates and lipids (Schroeder, 2024). Hence, the building blocks of life can and do form in space. It is not hard to believe the ability of the early organism to survive the crash with microbes has living implications. Scientists have found that bacteria, protected by endospores, can survive in Mars-type conditions. In the LICHENS experiment, some lichens could survive up to two weeks in space. Tardigrades, when entered cryptobiosis, can survive in outer space, freezing temperatures, and crushing points, and as soon as environments are optimal, revert to normal. Plus, there is another degree of protection as these microbes can tuck themselves into the interstices of rock and ice. Hence, as a primitive outer-space microorganism with a basic structure, it can use aspects of the harsh primitive Earth environment to its advantage and adapt to better fit its ever-changing environments.

3. On the Chemical Evolution

As of lately, the most accepted theory is chemical evolution, but there are still areas of vagueness and assumption. Simply, there are thermodynamic and chemical barriers to

the ability of Earth to produce its own life. Since Miller's experiment, other origins-of-life chemists have produced organic compounds under a variety of conditions, using various gases that simulated early Earth. Kenyon and Steinman stated, "The experiments discussed in this chapter indicate that a rich variety of biologically important molecules could have been synthesized on the primitive Earth by simple means." However, regarding the rates of destruction in the ocean, Miller and Orgel stated that "The rates of depurination of DNA, of hydrolysis of peptide and polynucleotide polymers, and decomposition of sugars, in the ocean, are so large that it seems impossible that such compounds could have accumulated in aqueous solution and have been used in the first organism unless the temperature was low." They state that a temperature of 0 Celsius would be acceptable and that -21°C would be optimal. However, the research of paleogeobiologist Garcia and her colleagues suggested that Earth's surface was roughly 75 Celsius 3 billion years ago and only reached 35 Celsius about 420 million years ago, but life was supposed to already exist 3.5 billion years ago (Choi, 2017). These findings are inconsistent with the ideal environments proposed by Miller and Orgel of 0 to -21 Celsius. Even if this issue is given the benefit of the doubt, the spontaneous linkage of amino acids into proteins or nucleotides into RNA is chemically unfavorable in water, which would have been abundant on the early Earth and thought to be the place of origin for life. This presents another significant problem of forming the complex molecules necessary for life, since water tends to break down these polymers back into their monomers in a hydrolysis reaction. Amino acids react with carbohydrates, with both destroyed, yet each would have been needed for the origin of life—amino acids to form proteins and sugars as constituents of DNA and RNA. Not to mention that all the phosphoric acid in the primitive ocean would have been precipitated as the insoluble calcium salt. Hence, these practical barriers need to be addressed if solo chemical evolution should remain a likelihood.

4. Panspermia and Chemical Evolution United

The theory of naturalistic panspermia, or Cosmozoic theory, suggests that life originated in space, and the theory of chemical evolution suggests that life originated on Earth. The two may not have to contradict each other, perhaps even cooperating to generate a better explanation for early life. After all, the primordial soup was an environment on Earth yet not specific to Earth, for it merely means a hypothetical set of environmental characteristics that described the volatile environment on primitive planets like Earth due to continuous interactions with the universe from collisions of all kinds. Even now, organic compounds are found that are made far from Earth. In a XANES or X-ray absorption near-edge structure analysis of the organic residues formed from

astrophysical ice analogs containing different combinations of water, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, methanol, ammonia, as well as hydrocyanic acid, oxygen, and nitrogen under UV photo-irradiation, there were also different combinations of molecular precursors of prebiotic interest such as amino acids, amphiphilic molecules, and others not limited to urea and glycerol. The study indicates, "when small aromatic species mix within the astrophysical ice analogs, molecules such as quinones and nucleobases, the informational units of DNA and RNA, are also formed." Likewise, a similar finding was identified in the Rosetta mission from comet C67/Churyumov-Gerasimenko. Scientists found that phosphorus and organic compounds like glycine comprised half of the comet, the rest being minerals. The COMetary Secondary Ion Mass Analyser (COSIMA) instrument collected and analyzed more than 35,000 escaping dust grains outgassed by Comet 67P. Martin Hilchenbach, the principal investigator of the COSIMA team, said, "Our analyses show that the composition of all these grains is very similar." The dust was likely made of the same ingredients as the nucleus. The external factor in this case would be the meteors that rained on Earth. Working with the idea of chemical evolution would have promoted the primordial soup and been essential for allowing an idea of chemical evolution to begin.

5. Ending remark

Given the above, panspermia is not a defeated theory of the origin of life and, in fact, holds more weight than the more popular chemical evolution. Acknowledging the vague exchange between meteors and Earth as well as a noticeable time gap before the first emergence of life, more research needs to be done on the exchange and extra care to be paid to opening human minds to the possibilities of extraterrestrial life. Humankind has yet to explore the validity of the Panspermia with the limited access it has to the universe. Professor of Astronomy Chris Impey states, "A universal theory of life is still elusive. Such a theory would include the concepts of complexity and information storage, but it would not be tied to DNA or the particular kinds of cells we find in terrestrial biology." Hence, an even wider scope beyond this article is probable, having removed the assumption that the first life must be in the familiar model of a microorganism. There are many possibilities, and so humankind should never cease looking to the sky.